

BEHAVIOR IN OPEN HOLE COMPRESSION (OHC) TESTS AND PROPOSAL OF SHORTER SPECIMEN

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ABSTRACT: Open Hole Compression (OHC) tests sometimes provide most critical strength data in composites structural design. However, its mechanics to failure is not well understood even at this time. In-situ observation of failure process at OHC tests of CFRP laminate using fiber optic microscope was conducted first and some important features of mechanics to failure were recognized. Fiber micro-buckling in 0-lamina is the most probable trigger of delamination onsets. Growth of fiber micro-buckling and other damage was identified by X-ray and ultrasonic NDE devices. A route to the final failure can be basically described. The final phase of the failure is controlled by delamination-buckling of the surface 45-lamina. Unidirectional compression strength of 0-lamina may affect OHC strengths. The final failure propagates transversely to the load quite similarly to compression-after-impact (CAI) tests. Early phase of numerical simulation has been undertaken. After the identification of failure mechanism, the authors' group found the cost-ineffectiveness in the current *de facto* standard method, SACMA SRM 3R-94 using very long specimen. Hence, a new method with shorter specimen and the same width and hole size is proposed in this paper. It is clarified that new methods provide almost the same data as SACMA and that it contributes cost reduction in composites evaluation very much.

KEYWORDS: Experiments, Fiber Micro-Buckling, In-Situ Observation, Specimen Economy, New Test Method

INTRODUCTION

Open Hole Compression (OHC) tests are regarded as one of the most important evaluation for aircraft composite structure design similarly to Compression after impact (CAI) tests. Allowable strain limit is mainly defined from OHC or CAI data for composite primary structures and they govern weight reduction ratios¹⁾. OHC tests sometimes conducted as material screening phase evaluating new composite system due to its polymer controlled nature. OHC tests provide lower cost measure of composites than CAI tests. Therefore, importance of OHC tests is enhanced in both aircraft and composite material industries. However, current *de facto* standard test method for OHC, SACMA SRM 3R-94²⁾, specifies longer size specimen of 304 mm and large complicated test fixtures. The final goal of this research program is, therefore, to establish a new test method using shorter specimens.

Prior to discuss the test method, deep understanding of failure mechanism in OHC tests is required in order to examine the effect of specimen length to the OHC strengths. In-situ observation of failure process by using fiber-optic microscope was conducted to understand what happens before failure. Several NDI devices were also used to clarify failure sequence. A featuring damage pattern in the initial phase is the fiber micro-buckling in 0-degree lamina at the hole edge. Failure sequence is roughly identified by these devices.

Numerical simulation of the OHC test has also been conducted although the current level stays at the linear elastic level. Even so, scenario of the initial fiber micro-buckling can be roughly described. Extended analysis of the progressive failure has been undertaken and some early results will be shown at the presentation.

By such examination of the failure process, it is clarified that the damage propagates transversely to the loads from the initial micro-buckling portion and that specimen length does not affect the behavior at all. Hence, it is worthwhile first to examine the possibility of the shorter specimen than SACMA 3R-94. NAL of Japan conducted a survey of the existing OHC test methods and proposed a new OHC test method (set of specimen, fixture and procedure), referred as NAL-III³. Key points in the specimen sizing are to maintain hole diameter to width ratio of SACMA in the new method and to reduce the length. The design of the fixture is another important point in the definition of the new method. The code number -III in the name denotes the third candidate tried in NAL. OHC test data based on SACMA and NAL-III were compared in the in-house scale preliminary program and they coincided well with each other. The program is now widened to national scale round robin tests to establish JIS (Japan Industrial Standard) for OHC tests. Hopefully, JIS OHC methods will be defined within a few years in Japan. This research program provides a mechanical foundation of the new test method.

EXPERIMENTAL FINDINGS IN OHC TESTS

Experimental findings mainly related to failure process understanding are given first. Before going into findings themselves, an outline of experimental procedure is explained. Four kinds of composites systems were used for OHC tests where all materials are carbon/epoxy based on prepreg and shown in Table 1. Adopted laminate construction is quasi-isotropic of 16 plies, $[(45/0/-45/90)_2]_{sym}$, where approximately 2.1-2.3 mm in thickness. Because the details of adopted test methods, SACMA 3R-94 and NAL-III will be described later, they will be intentionally skipped in this chapter. Only the key dimensions are stated here: 304 mm in length by 38.1 mm width with 6.35 mm diameter hole for SACMA and 118 mm in length by 38.1 mm width with 6.35 mm diameter hole for NAL-III. A small amount of exception in length took place for a case of IM600/QC133 NAL-III tests, i.e., 118 mm was shortened to 110 mm. These dimensions are illustrated in Fig.1 with the indication of strain gage locations. Gage location I in NAL-III has an offset of 2.14 mm in order to avoid peak in the serration of fixture surface. Gage location I in SACMA implies non back-to-back arrangement due to the design of SCAMA fixture. Test setup is shown in Fig.2 where one featuring device is a fiber-optic/CCD sensor microscope (VH-5910 by KEYENCE Ltd) for in-situ observation of failure process around the hole. This microscope is quite eligible to capture the active image of damage propagation in a micro-meso scale at in-situ state of the loaded specimen. Four channel trains were recorded almost 5 Hz by a multiplexer system, HP 34970A and stored into PC (by DELL Corp.).

Key parameters in the test procedure are as follows: Crosshead speeds are 1.0 mm/min. for SACMA and 0.38 mm/min. for NAL-III which reflects the length difference in specimens. Tightening torque of fixture screws are 0.5 Nm for SACMA, and finger tight and 0.6 Nm for NAL-III, i.e., two cases of torque were examined for NAL-III. Test environment was always room temperature and dry (RTD).

Table 1 Used Composites for OHC Tests

Material Code	Fabricated Company	Feature
IM600/QC101	Toho Tenax Co. LTD	IM Fiber, Slight High Temp. Epoxy
IM600/QC133	As above	IM Fiber, Toughened Epoxy
KA/410	Mitsubishi Rayon Co. LTD	Std. Fiber, 1 st Generation High Modulus Epoxy
T800H/3633	TORAY Co. LTD	IM Fiber, Toughened Epoxy

Fig.1 Specimen Dimensions and Strain Gage Locations in OHC Tests

Fig.2 Test Setup of OHC Tests

Typical stress-strain curves for four types of carbon/epoxy are shown in Figs.3 and 4 where plots in Fig.3 are confined to Strain I in Fig.1. Because this strain is somehow close to the far field

Fig.3 Typical Stress-Strain Curves for KA/410 and IM600/QC101

Fig.4 Typical Stress-Strain Curves for T800H/3633 and IM600/QC133

strain, the effect of local failure is weakly observed. Figure 4 depicts stress-strain (including Strain II) curves for the rest two material systems. Because strain II is strongly affected by the local damage around the hole, its nonlinear response is well observed.

Next, the core of the experimental findings will be described, that is, observed failure evolution process by the fiber-optic CCD microscope. Figure 5 depicts the pictures taken at the indicated load level for IM600/epoxy's. Fiber micro-buckling is observed at some low level of load

IM600/QC101			
Load	A 4.0kN	B 21.8kN	C 23.0kN
IM600/QC133			
Load	D 6.0kN	E 21.5kN	F 23.5kN

Fig.5 Typical Stress-Strain Curves for T800H/3633 and IM600/QC133

around 4 – 7 kN. The load levels corresponding to each picture are indicated in Fig.6, load - end displacement curve. As can be seen, surface delamination buckling is initiated after 80 % of OHC strength and propagated around 90 %. This situation is more clear in Fig.7, results of ultrasonic C-scan of OHC specimens. It should be noted that this figure is not created by in-situ condition. In other words, OHC specimens were loaded to specified load level and unloaded, then C-scan was conducted. Thus, the strength data of these tests were

Fig.6 Load-Displacement Curve

excluded from the true OHC strengths shown later. It can be also understood that the fiber micro-buckling area does not expand so widely by the delamination initiation load. Simpler finding is that damage propagates transversely to the load by the time of failure like CAI tests¹⁾. Hence, speculation about effectiveness of shorter specimen is almost proven. Through a detailed observation of video-recorded data, hypothesis that the surface delamination is triggered by the damage point of fiber micro-buckling in 0-lamina can be suggested. In order to prove this hypothesis, detailed numerical simulation would be required. Although numerical simulation level presented in this paper is only elementary, the laborious nonlinear simulation work is now undertaken. In the near future, the results could be presented.

Fig.7 Trace of Delamination Propagation by Ultrasonic C-scan

COMAPRISON OF OHC STRENGTH DATA BY SACMA AND NAL-III METHODS

After the identification of several experimental findings, the core incentive of the current research must be discussed. At the first step of comparison, details of the two methods are reviewed. The specimen size is already shown in Fig.1. Here, the picture and idea of the test fixture of SACMA 3R-94 is shown first in Fig.8. This main fixture was originally designed for clamping by a large hydraulic grip and a compression load is introduced into the specimen by shear from the surface in the original idea. Detailed drawings are given in the SACMA document. However, SACMA 3R-94 also allows end loading under the usage of sub-fixture by which clamping force to the specimen can be generated. About the sub-fixture, no exact definition is given in the document and it is left the matter of user’s discretion. So, shown sub-fixtures with four bolts in Fig. 8 are mere example. It can be

Fig.8 Picture and Concept of Fixtures of SACMA 3R-94

Fig.9 Picture and Concept of Fixtures of NAL-III

imagined that the handling of fixtures is so bad due to their heavy weight. Of course, the main incentive of the invention of NAL-III fixture shown in Fig.9 is a reduction in specimen length to cut specimen cost into almost one third of SACMA. The idea is borrowed from plastic compression test of ASTM D695 and the window size is equalized to SACMA. Upper and lower sub-fixtures are designed for preventing end brooming failure mode. However, because OHC strengths are considerably lower than end brooming failure strength as usual, these sub-fixtures are almost a kind of insurance. In some high temperature test cases, they may be really required. In the recent version of main fixtures of ASTM D695 type, cutouts in the serration peak are introduced for securing strain gage space.

All the results of OHC tests are shown in Fig.10 where filled and open legends correspond to SACMA and NAL-III methods, respectively. Almost no difference can be found in the results by both methods. For T800H/3633 carbon/epoxy, three cases of tightening torque of serrated fixture screws were examined, finger tight (approximately 0.1Nm), 0.3 and 0.6 Nm. The comparison indicates that no clear effect can be found within the tested range of torque. The average and standard deviation data based on the results in Fig.10 are listed in Table 2 and the averages of OHC strengths are graphically shown in Fig.10. The finding in Fig.10 of similarity in strengths is statistically confirmed by these table and figure. This coincidence is very natural if damage propagation mode indicated in Fig.7 is reminded.

The other finding related to composite system can be also seen in these data, i.e., higher OHC strengths in KA/410 carbon/epoxy. As explained earlier, this composite system belongs to the first generation carbon/epoxy, which employs quite brittle and high modulus epoxy resin. CAI strengths of this composites system are almost half³⁾ of modern toughened carbon epoxy like IM600/QC133 or T800H/3633. However, OHC strengths of this traditional system is quite higher than those modern

Fig. 10 All Tests Data Plots of OHC Strengths by Two Methods

Table 2 Average and Std. Deviation of OHC Strength

Composites Name	Method	Averaged Strengths	Std. Deviation
A (IM600/QC101)	SACMA	274.38	4.24
	NAL-III	271.32	4.98
B (IM600/QC133)	SACMA	284.97	6.90
	NAL-III	271.98	7.40
C (KA/410)	SACMA	368.86	5.67
	NAL-III	370.18	1.89
D (T800H/3633)	SACMA	305.85	11.72
	NAL-III	295.18	4.20

Fig.11 Graphical Average

systems. According to advanced composites database^{4,5)} constructed by NAL (NAL-ACDB), unidirectional compression strengths of KA/410 is somewhat larger than modern systems. Again, one hypothesis that higher UD compressive strength leads to higher OHC strength can be derived. A proof is also left to the future examination by laborious numerical simulations.

OUTLINE OF ELEMENTARY NUMERICAL ANALYSIS OF OHC TEST

In order to understand the damage propagation explained in the previous chapters, numerical analysis has been conducted by using a finite element method (FEM). However, the current level still stays at the linear elastic approach. So, the first target is to predict or explain the initial fiber micro-buckling occurring at considerably low stress level. The used code is a general purpose FEM package, ANSYS ver.5.7, and adopted element is a nonlinear laminate shell type, SHELL 91 in ANSYS. Element partitioning and boundary conditions are shown in Fig.12 where yellow arrows in the lower chart indicate constraints to the z-direction (out-of plane) deflection. These boundary conditions are set to reflect fixture constraints with a 25.4 by 16.5 mm window as much as possible.

The selected composite system as analysis target is IM600/QC133 and its elastic properties are listed in Table 3 based on advanced composites database, NAL-ACDB⁵⁾ where the minor Poisson's ratio with asterisk was borrowed from other CF/epoxy data of modern resin.

The calculated stress-strain relations are shown in Fig.13 with a comparison to the experimental data. Due to the linearity in the analysis, the calculated strain response is of course linear and its plotting is truncated at the experimental strength level. At strain II location, 5 mm offset from the hole center

Fig.12 Element Partitioning in Linear FEM Analysis

Table 3 Input Orthotropic Elastic Moduli of IM600/QC133

Elastic properties of unidirectional IM600/QC133			
Longitudinal modulus,	E_L	[GPa]	154.00
Transverse modulus,	E_T	[GPa]	8.06
Shear modulus,	G_{LT}	[GPa]	4.70
Poisson's ratio,	ν_{LT}		0.348
	ν_{TZ}		0.456*

Fig.13 Comparison between Numerical and Experimental Stress-Strain Response

on the crossing centerline, strain data over 220MPa was affected by local delamination buckling also as shown in Fig.4 right. However, up to this stress level, the present simplest approach can predict macroscopic stress-strain behavior. In order to provide a baseline knowledge about fiber micro-buckling discussion lamina-level relative stress distribution in the fiber direction normalized by the far-field compression stress is given in Fig.14. Stress concentration factor of approximately 8 (8.10) is observed in 0-lamina at the hole edge. This high stress concentration is definitely the main cause of early fiber micro-buckling in the 0-lamina observed through the fiber-optic microscope. Schematic explanation of the behavior is presented in Fig.15 where the magnified view of micro-buckling and a stress distribution chart in the fiber direction in the 0-lamina are indicated. So, the behavior can be understood qualitatively. If we look at the behavior somewhat quantitatively, the initiation stress level information of the fiber micro-buckling has to be required. Due to the current microscope memory system, it is not a simple work and rough estimation was conducted. The average of micro-buckling initiation stress is **66 MPa** for IM600/133 where high scatter in the results is observed. Then, the **535 MPa** can be obtained as the local 0-lamina stress by a simple multiplication of 8.10. According to the database, NAL-ACDB⁵⁾, the unidirectional compression strength of IM600/QC133(8 plies, SACMA SRM 1R-94) is **1037 MPa**. Thus, there can be found a double discrepancy between a simple estimation and experimental stress level if we assume that fiber micro-buckling is initiated by the local 0-lamina compressive failure. For further rigorous discussions,

Fig.14 Relative Stress Concentration in the Fiber Direction on the Centerline

Fig.15 Schematic Explanation of Mechanism of Fiber Micro-Buckling

improvement in the experimental determination of buckling onset stress and grading-up in the numerical analysis are both required. These efforts are now undertaken and the results will be presented hopefully soon.

CONCLUSIONS

OHC tests of four types of carbon/epoxy laminates were conducted with in-situ observation of failure process using fiber optic microscope. Some important findings in mechanics to failure were recognized. Fiber micro-buckling at considerably low stress level was observed in 0-lamina and it is the most probable trigger of delamination onsets. Growth of fiber micro-buckling and other damage was identified by fiber-optic microscope and ultrasonic NDE devices. A route to the final failure can be basically described. The final phase of the failure is initiated by delamination-buckling of the surface 45-lamina. If OHC data are compared among four types of laminates, unidirectional compression strength of 0-lamina may affect OHC strengths. The important finding is that the final failure propagates transversely to the load quite similarly to compression-after-impact (CAI) tests. Hence, the extra length in specimen does not affect OHC data at all.

Thus, justification of shorter length specimen is obtained and a new test method with a specimen of 118 mm in length and identical width and hole diameter to the current *de facto* standard, SACMA SRM 3R-94, is proposed with a nomination of NAL-III. The other feature of this method is its fixture based on the same idea as ASTM-D695 and the same window size as SACMA. Comparison of the results for all composite laminates leads to the conclusion that SACMA and NAL-III provide almost identical strengths. This conclusion is compatible with the finding of transverse damage propagation to the loads. The new methods will bring a great test cost reduction due to its shorter size of specimen.

Elementary linear finite element analysis is conducted by using ANSYS. The results coincide with the experimental data within linear behavior range. A stress concentration factor of 8.10 is identified in 0-lamina at the hole edge. A qualitative explanation of fiber micro-buckling at lower stress level is given based on this knowledge. However, early quantitative comparison between peak stress in 0-lamina and its compressive strength describes a serious discrepancy. More improved experiment, analysis and scenario will be required to full description of the mechanics.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to express their sincere gratitude to the student (at that time) who supported the early part of OHC tests, Mr. E. Hara. This work is supported by NAL program of foundation and standardization of new composites test methods.

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